

The Smarandache-Coman function and nine conjectures on it

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Abstract. The Smarandache-Coman function is the function defined on the set of non-null positive integers with values in the set of non-null positive integers in the following way: $SC(n)$ is the least number such that $SC(n)!$ is divisible by $n + r$, where r is the digital root of the number n . In other words, $SC(n) = S(n + r)$, where S is the Smarandache function. I also state, in this paper, nine conjectures on this function which seems to be particularly interesting: beside other characteristics, it seems to have as values all the prime numbers and, more than that, they seem to appear, leaving aside the non-prime values, in natural order.

Definition:

The Smarandache-Coman function is the function defined on the set of non-null positive integers with values in the set of non-null positive integers in the following way: $SC(n)$ is the least number such that $SC(n)!$ is divisible by $n + r$, where r is the digital root of the number n . In other words, $SC(n) = S(n + r)$, where S is the Smarandache function.

Note: The digital root of a number is obtained through the iterative operation of summation of the digits of a number until is obtained a single digit; examples: the digital root of the number 28 is 1 because $2 + 8 = 10$ and $1 + 0 = 1$; the digital root of the number 1729 is 1 because $1 + 7 + 2 + 9 = 19$ and $1 + 9 = 10$ and $1 + 0 = 1$; the digital root of the number 561 is 3 because $5 + 6 + 1 = 12$ and $1 + 2 = 3$; so, the digital root of a number can only have one from the following nine values: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 or 9.

The values of SC function are:

: 2, 4, 3, 4, 5, 4, 7, 8, 6, 11, 13, 5, 17, 19, 7, 23,
10, 9, 5, 11, 6, 13, 7, 5, 8, 17, 6, 29, 31, 11, 7,
37, 13, 41, 43, 6, 19, 5, 7, 11, 23, 6, 10, 13, 9,
47, 7, 17, 53, 11, 19, 59, 61, 7, 7, 29, 5, 31, 8,
11, 17, 7, 6, 13, 67, 23, 71, 73, 10, 11, 79, 9, 37,
19, 13, 6, 41, 7, 43, 11, 6, 83, 17, 29, 89, 13, 31,
19, 97 (...)

Observation 1:

Within the first 89 values of SC(n) are found all the first 25 primes from 2 to 97. More than that, they all appear for the first time in order: there is not a prime $p_3 > p_2$ between p_1 and p_2 , where $p_1 < p_2$ and both p_1 and p_2 appear for the first time in Smarandache-Coman sequence.

Observation 2:

Note that, from the first 89 values of SC(n):

- : 69 are primes (25 of them distinct);
- : 3 are odd non-primes (all of them equal to 9);
- : 17 are even non-primes (4 of them distinct: 4, 6, 8, 10).

Observation 3:

Up to $n = 89$, the longest chain of consecutive prime values of SC(n) is obtained for n from 46 to 58: 47, 7, 17, 53, 11, 19, 59, 61, 7, 7, 29, 5, 31.

Conjecture 1:

All the prime numbers appear as values in the SC sequence (the sequence of the values of SC function).

Conjecture 2:

All the prime numbers appear for the first time in natural order in SC sequence: : there is not a prime $p_3 > p_2$ between p_1 and p_2 , where $p_1 < p_2$ and both p_1 and p_2 appear for the first time in SC sequence.

Conjecture 3:

All the even numbers appear as values in the SC sequence.

Conjecture 4:

There exist an infinity of primes p for which $SC(p) = q$, where q is prime.

The sequence of the primes (p, q) is:

- : (1, 2), (3, 3), (5, 5), (7, 7), (11, 13), (13, 17), (23, 7), (29, 31), (31, 7), (37, 19), (41, 23), (47, 7), (53, 61), (61, 17), (67, 71), (71, 79), (73, 37), (79, 43), (83, 17), (89, 97)...

Conjecture 5:

For all the pairs of twin primes (p, q) , where $p \geq 11$, is true that, if p appears for the first time in SC sequence as $SC(n)$, then $SC(n + 1) = q$.

Conjecture 6:

There exist an infinity of numbers n such that $SC(n) = m$ and $SC(n + 1) = m + 1$, where $m + 1$ is prime. Such pairs of $(m, m + 1)$ are: $(10, 11)$, $(28, 29)$, $(46, 47)$, $(82, 83)$...

Conjecture 7:

There exist an infinity of numbers n such that $SC(n) = m$ and $SC(n + 1) = m - 9$, where $m - 9$ is prime. Such pairs of $(m, m - 9)$ are: $(20, 11)$, $(22, 13)$, $(26, 17)$...

Conjecture 8:

There exist an infinity of values primes p of $SC(n)$ for which the sum s of all the values of $SC(n)$ up to and including $SC(p)$ is prime. Such pairs of (p, s) are: $(7, 29)$, $(13, 67)$, $(17, 89)$, $(11, 173)$, $(7, 199)$, $(17, 229)$, $(7, 313)$, $(13, 547)$, $(11, 691)$, $(59, 769)$, $(13, 971)$, $(23, 1061)$, $(17, 1597)$, $(97, 1877)$...

Conjecture 9:

There exist an infinity of pairs $(p = S(n), r = S(n + 2))$, both p and r primes which appear for the first time in SC sequence, with the property that $r = p + 4$, such that $q = S(n + 1)$ is prime. Such triplets (p, q, r) are: $(13, 5, 17)$, $(19, 7, 23)$, $(37, 13, 41)$, $(67, 23, 71)$...